

MODELLING OF THE THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOVEN COMPOSITES DURING THE CURE

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1 Introduction

Woven fabrics are used more widely in composite materials as reinforcements to manufacture complex structures due to their high drapability and good impact resistance compared to unidirectional fibres. Understanding the properties of woven composites and their evolution during the cure is therefore important in terms of design and manufacturing of complex composite structures using woven fabrics.

Properties of fabric reinforcements have been studied over the past decades. Ishikawa and Chou [1-5] developed three analytical models to predict the thermo-mechanical properties of woven composites: the mosaic, the crimp and the bridging models. These models described the fabric as an assemblage of cross-ply laminates with no fibre undulation (mosaic model), few undulation (bridging model, more suitable for satin fabric) and shape function to describe the fibre waviness (crimp model, more suitable for plain weave fabric). However, these models are restricting the fabric to undulation in only one dimension. Two dimensional plain weave composite models were also developed by Naik and Shembekar [6, 7], Shembekar and Naik [8], Ganesh and Naik [9] and Naik and Ganesh [10, 11]. They showed that the mechanical properties of the woven composites were affected by intrinsic characteristics of the fabric architecture, such as the undulation length, the gap between two adjacent tows or the ply thickness. Therefore, the fabric architecture could be optimized to improve the properties of woven fabric composites. More recently, finite element analysis (FEA) was used to calculate the effective mechanical properties of woven composites as well as internal strains, stresses and displacements at the unit cell level [12, 13]. Moreover, by combining FEA with process modeling analysis, the evolution of the internal

strains and stresses, and the thermo-mechanical properties as the cure progresses can be computed and the process-induced stresses and deformations can be predicted [14-16].

In this study, thermo-mechanical properties (i.e. effective stiffness, coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), residual stresses) of periodic 5-harness satin (5HS) woven fabric composite material were investigated and predicted during the cure, using a micromechanical approach based on finite element method that utilizes a 3D unit cell.

2 Finite element model and methodology

2.1 Unit cell geometry

The 5HS woven composite unit cell was created using TexGen, a software dedicated to the modelling of textile structure in 3D. The unit cell dimensions were based on the geometrical parameters of a four-ply laminate manufactured by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) with G30-500-6k 5HS carbon fibre and CYCOM 890RTM epoxy resin. The unit cell volumes were then imported and meshed in ABAQUS finite element software, as shown in Fig. 1. The unit cell was generated with 70% fibre volume fraction tow and an overall fibre volume fraction with the resin rich region of 50%. The unit cell constituents, resin and fibre, were defined by two material sections. The different fibre orientations were defined in reference to two local rectangular coordinate systems (x,y,z) and (x',y',z') , (see Fig. 1b). These local coordinate systems were generated so that x and x' axes always remained in the direction of the fibres and the out-of-plane axes z and z' always remained normal to the element surface to take into account the fibre waviness (Fig. 1d.).

Fig. 1: 5HS unit cell: a) 2D view, b) unit cell finite element model and dimensions, c) tow dimensions, and d) schematic representation of the fibre orientation along a tow

2.2 Model boundary conditions

In the present study it is assumed that a perfect bonding between the fibre and the resin exists and no contact interactions were used at the fibre/resin interface.

Then, to satisfy the equivalence of elastic energies and continuity of displacement at the unit cell level and composite material level, periodic boundary conditions were applied to the unit cell so that it represents the periodic woven fabric composite material [17-22]. Periodic constraint equations were

thus applied on the nodes of opposite faces of the unit cell in the three global directions.

The periodic constraint equations for the opposite faces were defined as follows [17]:

$$u_i^{F_2} - u_i^{N_{246}} = u_i^{F_1} - u_i^{N_{146}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

$$u_i^{F_3} - u_i^{N_{136}} = u_i^{F_4} - u_i^{N_{146}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (2)$$

$$u_i^{F_5} - u_i^{N_{145}} = u_i^{F_6} - u_i^{N_{146}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

These equations ensure that the opposite faces F_1 and F_2 , F_3 and F_4 , F_5 and F_6 remain parallel for any loading conditions. Similarly, periodic constraints on the opposite edges were expressed in the following manner [17]:

$$u_i^{E_{15}} - u_i^{N_{145}} = u_i^{E_{25}} - u_i^{N_{245}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (4)$$

$$u_i^{E_{16}} - u_i^{N_{146}} = u_i^{E_{26}} - u_i^{N_{246}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (5)$$

$$u_i^{E_{14}} - u_i^{N_{146}} = u_i^{E_{24}} - u_i^{N_{246}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (6)$$

$$u_i^{E_{13}} - u_i^{N_{136}} = u_i^{E_{23}} - u_i^{N_{236}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (7)$$

$$u_i^{E_{36}} - u_i^{N_{136}} = u_i^{E_{46}} - u_i^{N_{146}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (8)$$

$$u_i^{E_{35}} - u_i^{N_{135}} = u_i^{E_{45}} - u_i^{N_{145}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (9)$$

$$u_i^{E_{23}} - u_i^{N_{236}} = u_i^{E_{24}} - u_i^{N_{246}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (10)$$

$$u_i^{E_{45}} - u_i^{N_{145}} = u_i^{E_{46}} - u_i^{N_{146}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (11)$$

$$u_i^{E_{25}} - u_i^{N_{245}} = u_i^{E_{26}} - u_i^{N_{246}} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (12)$$

Finally, seven different loading conditions (three axial strains, three shear strain and one thermal change) were applied to the model, as seen in Fig. 2. These axial loading conditions enabled the determination of the three effective moduli E_1 , E_2 and E_3 as well as the Poisson's ratios ν_{12} , ν_{13} , ν_{23} ; while the shear loading were used to compute the three effective shear moduli G_{12} , G_{13} , G_{23} . The coefficients of thermal expansion were determined from the thermal boundary conditions.

2.3 Methodology

A schematic visualization of the methodology is presented in Fig. 3. In order to understand the evolution of the composite properties and the development of the residual stresses as the cure progresses, the tow and resin properties were implemented in a material database subroutine, COMPRO, from Convergent Manufacturing Technologies Inc. The resin constitutive models, i.e resin cure kinetics, glass transition temperature, CTE, chemical shrinkage and elastic modulus were developed in a previous study published by the authors [23]. The tow properties were computed assuming a hexagonal packing configuration of the fibre within the tow and the thermo-mechanical material properties are reported in Table 1.

Heat transfer analysis was first performed using ABAQUS finite element software and the resin manufacturer recommended cure cycle, to calculate the evolution of the degree-of-cure with the cure cycle. Then, stress analyses, using different boundary conditions described in the section 2.2, were performed to compute the stress and strain generated in the material during the cure cycle, based on the evolution of the degree-of-cure.

The nine engineering material constants were finally extracted for different degree-of-cure, using the generalized Hooke's law, applied for orthotropic materials, as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_1 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_2 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_3 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_4 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_5 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{C}_{11} & \tilde{C}_{12} & \tilde{C}_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{12} & \tilde{C}_{22} & \tilde{C}_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{13} & \tilde{C}_{23} & \tilde{C}_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\epsilon}_1 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_2 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_3 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_4 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_5 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

with the effective elastic compliance equal to:

$$[\tilde{C}_{ij}]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_3} & \frac{1}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{23}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{13}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Using the axial and shear loading cases described earlier, strains $\tilde{\epsilon}_j$ are applied to the unit cell, and the resulting six components of the stresses can be computed at the fixed corner nodes (master nodes) of the unit cell. Knowing the average strains and

stresses, the engineering constants are calculated using equation 2.

For the temperature load, the Hooke's law was modified as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_1 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_2 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_3 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_4 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_5 \\ \tilde{\sigma}_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{C}_{11} & \tilde{C}_{12} & \tilde{C}_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{12} & \tilde{C}_{22} & \tilde{C}_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{13} & \tilde{C}_{23} & \tilde{C}_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\epsilon}_1 - \alpha_1 \Delta T \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_2 - \alpha_2 \Delta T \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_3 - \alpha_3 \Delta T \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_4 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_5 \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where α_i is the coefficient of thermal expansion.

Using the thermal boundary condition with no applied deformation ($\tilde{\epsilon}_j = 0$), the coefficient of thermal expansion were determined.

Fig. 2: Boundary conditions: a) for axial loading, b) for shear loading, c) for thermal loading

Fig. 3: Methodology overview

Table 1: Carbon fibre and epoxy resin properties

Carbon fibre G30-500 6k [25, 26]	Cured epoxy resin CYCOM 890RTM [27]	Computed tow properties, fully cured $V_f = 70\%$	Computed 5HS unit cell properties, fully cured $V_f = 50\%$
$E_{1f} = 230$ GPa	$E_r = 3.1$ GPa	$E_1 = 161.76$ GPa	$E_1 = E_2 = 59.44$ GPa
$E_{2f} = E_{3f} = 22$ GPa		$E_2 = E_3 = 9.98$ GPa	$E_3 = 7.72$ GPa
$\nu_{12f} = \nu_{13f} = 0.3$	$\nu_r = 0.2$	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$	$\nu_{12} = 0.054$
$\nu_{23f} = 0.35$		$\nu_{23} = 0.362$	$\nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.388$
$G_{12f} = G_{13f} = 22$ GPa	$G_r = 1.2$ GPa	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.29$ GPa	$G_{12} = 3.97$ GPa
$G_{23f} = 8.15$ GPa		$G_{23} = 3.66$ GPa	$G_{13} = G_{23} = 2.65$ GPa
$CTE_{1f} = -0.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$CTE_r = 55 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$CTE_1 = -0.37 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$CTE_1 = CTE_2 = 2.94 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
$CTE_{2f} = CTE_{3f} = 8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$		$CTE_2 = CTE_3 = 23.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$CTE_3 = 47.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

*The subscripts “f” and “r” stand for fibre and resin respectively.

1, 2 and 3 correspond to the three principal direction of the material

3 Results and discussion

The thermo-mechanical properties of the fully cured tow and the 5HS unit cell (degree-of-cure of 100%), calculated using the methodology described in section 2.3, are reported in Table 1. As expected, the 5HS unit cell properties are orthotropic, with $E_1 = E_2$, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$ and $G_{13} = G_{23}$.

Fig. 4 presents the evolution of the resin degree-of-cure and glass transition temperature predicted with the applied cure cycle. The gel point happened after 70 minutes for a degree-of-cure of 0.7. After two hours at 180°C, the resin has reached its maximum degree-of-cure.

Fig. 5, Fig. 7 and Fig. 7 show the evolution of the elastic modulus, the shear modulus and the coefficient of thermal expansion with the degree-of-cure for the composite unit cell. A significant change in property can be observed around a degree-of-cure of 0.7 which corresponds to the gel point of the resin. Before the gel point, the resin is in its liquid state with a low elastic modulus, a low shear modulus and a high CTE. At the gel point, the cross-linking network is developed and the resin has evolved from a liquid to a rubbery state. This change in physical state leads to a significant increase in elastic and shear modulus and a decrease in CTE. After the gel point, as the cure continues to progress, the resin reaches its glassy state, with a slight increase in mechanical properties.

Fig. 4: Predicted degree-of-cure and glass transition temperature for the resin manufacturer recommended cycle.

Fig. 5: Evolution of 5HS composite elastic modulus with degree-of-cure

Fig. 6: Evolution of 5HS composite shear modulus with degree-of-cure

Fig. 7: Evolution of 5HS composite CTE with degree-of-cure

Fig. 8: Development of composite internal stress in direction 1

The evolution of the internal stresses in the unit cell can be visualized in the global coordinate (x, y, z) in Fig. 8. Three main stage of the cure were chosen: gel point ($t = 70$ min), end of the isotherm ($t = 120$ min), end of the cure cycle ($t = 275$ min). The unit cell was cut along the yz plane in order to observe the state of stress inside the unit cell as well. Before the gel point, negligible stresses were present in the unit cell. Small compressive stresses arose after the gel point due to the resin shrinkage at the tow overlap (Fig. 8a). These stresses then increased with a maximum stress around 20 MPa at the end of the isotherm (Fig. 8b). The maximum stresses are also located where the tows are overlapping. At the end of the cure cycle the fibres remained in compression with compressive stresses around 50 to 100 MPa while the resin is in tension in the in-plane direction (Fig. 8c). These internal stresses generated during the cure cycle can be detrimental for the performance of the composite structure. Combined with the stresses that can arise from tool-part interaction, they can lead to the generation of residual stresses and part distortions, and ultimately early failure of a composite part [24].

4 Conclusions

In this study, the development of the thermo-mechanical properties of 5HS fabric composite with degree-of-cure was modelled. This analysis enabled the evaluation of the generation of internal stresses as the cure progresses, during a typical cure cycle. In this case studied, the generation of compressive stresses located at the tow overlap was observed during the cure. At the end of the cure, the unit cell state of stress predicted by the model was fibre in compression and resin in tension. This prediction is essential to understand the effect of material parameters on performance (residual stresses) and quality (distortions) of a composite part after processing.

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